

A STUDY ON HRD PRACTICES (T&D) IN IT SERVICES, HYDERABAD

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Abstract

Human Resource is the department responsible for overseeing employees and ensuring that they are treated fairly and professionally in the workplace. It has become an integral part of many businesses and has been the focal point of comprehensive discussions on the state of modern corporate partnerships. Managing human resources and developing them through creative practices is a crucial part of coordinating and managing work in every organisation. The study explores empirically the concept of training and training needs, and the factors influencing training requirements of the employees of IT Services in Hyderabad. Objectives have been framed and hypothesis has been set for testing statistical tool t test has been adopted and the results of the same have been presented and concluded accordingly.

Keywords: Human resource, relationships, employees, IT companies, innovative practices

Introduction:

Training, as said, focuses on enhancing employees' knowledge and skills for doing certain tasks, while development targets employees' overall growth. Training programmes that are both successful and efficient help employees prepare for and respond to future issues in a timely manner, creating a positive and productive work environment (Tai, 2006). Managers can't expect their employees to learn what they're supposed to if they don't know what they hope to learn, what their specific training needs are, and what makes for an effective training design—all of which are at the heart of the organization's goals. Before presenting a training programme to employees, it is important to determine the program's need and objectives. (Obisi, 2001).

“Training is an ongoing process of enhancing one's wisdom and capability in order to do a specific job.” — Edwin B. Flippo

Training is a planned process that helps workers acquire the knowledge and abilities they need to do their jobs effectively. That is to say, through training, employees are given the opportunity to expand their specialized knowledge and acquire the abilities necessary to perform their

professions. Employees, both new and old, benefit just as much from training. It helps new hires learn the ropes and develop expertise in areas relevant to their current position.

The purpose of training the employees arises due to the various reasons:

(i) Higher Productivity:

Workers' output can be boosted by proper training that provides them with the necessary skills.

(ii) Quality Improvement:

Consumers today place a premium on high-quality goods, and their needs are always evolving. Training employees is essential to maintaining a high standard of quality in order to keep consumers satisfied.

(iii) Reduction of Learning Time:

Training time can be shortened by employing a systematic approach delivered by qualified instructors.

(iv) Reduction of Turnover and Absenteeism:

Workers gain self-assurance as a result of receiving training. This ensures their safety in the workplace.

(vi) Technology Update:

The pace of technological development is increasing. Workers need training in new skills to take advantage of technological advances.

(vii) Effective Management:

Planning and controlling processes can benefit from training. It helps employees grow professionally so they may do better in their current and future positions.

Review of Literature

1. **G.P. Nunvi (2006)** emphasized the difference between training and development, with the former focusing on enhancing present-day performance and the latter on creating opportunities for employment in the future. Due to technological advancements, some human activities have been rendered obsolete and replaced by machines. Those in current positions, as well as those seeking promotions in the future, will need to continue their education and improve their skills.
2. **Armstrong (1996)**, training is best appreciated when it is produced and used internally by valuing the knowledge gained from many perspectives and methods. When people

take part in something, they usually end up shaping the circumstances surrounding it or the way something works. The same may be said for educating staff members.

3. **Birdi (2005)** considered to be the act of passing on knowledge and expertise from an experienced individual to a novice student. Both the worker who requests training and the trainer or staff member who actually provides it are crucial to this exchange. As a result of their role in training's prearrangement and post-quality evaluation, the authorities conducting training and providing resources to it constitute as a third party.
4. **Sims (1990)** focused on a more all-encompassing approach to training and development, citing the following as areas in which its effects can be felt strongly: 1. Employees' focus on profits 2. expertise in the field 3. proficiency in all facets of administration Boosted morale among employees 5. A sense of shared purpose among workers Training has a demotivating effect on employees. Workers are more likely to put forth effort into their work and responsibilities after receiving adequate training.
5. **Singh, C. and Jain, K. V. (2017)** The investigators of the study recognized that training and development are time-consuming and expensive, but concluded that the benefits to the individual and the company outweigh the costs.

Objectives of the study:

1. To understand the theoretical aspects of training and training needs of **IT Services, Hyderabad**
2. To study the factors influencing training programmes organized by **IT Services**

Research methodology

Primary Data

Making use of a questionnaire, primary data has been collected for the purpose of gathering information on par with the objectives of the study with the help of a structured questionnaire

Secondary Data

The requirements of the data are the details regarding the following by select IT companies factors influencing training programmes organized by **IT Services** in Hyderabad. Surf engines, journals and magazines have been sourced for the study.

Sample size: **533**

Sampling technique: Simple random Sampling

Limitations of the study:

- The study is limited to Hyderabad topography only
- Among innovative practices only training and development in **IT Services** has been considered for the study
- The data provided by the respondents may be biased

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive statistics

Tab-1 Frequency Distribution of Marital Status of Select IT Companies

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Unmarried	289	54.2
Married	244	45.8
Total	533	100.0

Analysis: The above table shows that 54.2% of the employees of **IT Services** of the sample study are unmarried and 45.8% are married.

Tab-2 Frequency Distribution of Gender of Select IT Company Employees

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	300	56.3
Female	233	43.7
Total	533	100.0

Analysis: It is evident from the above table that 56.3% of the employees of the sample study are working with the select **IT Services** are males and the remaining 43.7% are females.

Inferential statistics

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between gender and factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by **IT Services**

Tab- 3: t test for significant difference between gender and factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT Services

Factors	Gender				t value	P value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Training Policy	30.33	2.42	30.85	2.44	2.471	0.004*%
Attitude of the Top Management	30.15	2.25	30.72	2.24	2.915	0.004**
Training Need Analysis	13.14	1.45	13.47	1.30	2.680	0.008**
Working environment and facilities	34.56	2.44	34.91	2.57	1.589	0.003**
Overall Pre-Training Initiatives	108.19	6.17	109.95	6.51	3.200	<0.001**
Opinion about Trainers	26.66	2.45	27.03	2.17	1.816	0.007**
Opinion on Training Methods	39.35	2.86	40.06	2.79	2.890	0.004**
Accountability and Reward	30.78	2.88	31.30	2.70	2.126	0.003**
Feedback about Training	35.19	2.94	35.84	2.93	2.552	0.002**
Overall Effectiveness of Training Programmes	131.97	9.52	134.23	8.82	2.804	0.005**

Indicates significant at 1% level

Analysis: As the probability value is seen to be lesser than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives and overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT companies. Hence there is significance difference between gender and level of agreement with respect to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives taken by them and all the factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT companies

Based on mean score, the females show a higher level of agreement with respect to all the factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives and overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by **IT Services**

Hypothesis-2

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between marital status and factors influencing overall effectiveness of Training Programmes organized by **IT Services**

Tab- 4: t test for significant difference between marital status and factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT Services

Factors	Marital Status				t value	P value
	Unmarried		Married			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Training Policy	30.41	2.38	30.73	2.51	1.519	0.009**
Attitude of the Top Management	30.34	2.08	30.48	2.45	0.711	0.007**
Training Need Analysis	13.21	1.38	13.37	1.41	1.336	0.008**
Working environment and facilities	34.48	2.48	34.99	2.50	2.360	0.002**
Overall Pre-Training Initiatives	108.44	5.87	109.57	6.89	2.053	0.003**
Opinion about Trainers	26.58	2.41	27.10	2.21	2.601	0.008**
Opinion on Training Methods	39.30	2.95	40.08	2.66	3.182	0.007**
Accountability and Reward	30.78	2.85	31.28	2.74	2.083	0.1006*
Feedback about Training	35.27	3.03	35.71	2.85	1.700	0.002**
Overall Effectiveness of Training Programmes	131.93	9.37	134.18	9.03	2.806	0.005**

Indicates significant at 1% level

Analysis: As the probability value is seen to be lesser than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regard to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives and overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT Services. Hence there is significance difference between marital status and level of agreement with respect to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives taken by them and all the factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by them. Based on mean score, the married employees IT Services show a higher level of agreement with respect to all the factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives and overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by IT Services

Conclusions

1. There is significance difference between gender and level of agreement with respect to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives taken by private banks and all the

factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by select IT companies with females show a higher level of agreement

2. There is significance difference between marital status and level of agreement with respect to factors influencing overall pre-training initiatives taken by private banks and all the factors influencing overall effectiveness of training programmes organized by select IT companies with married employees showing higher level of agreement.
3. A mismatch in training requires status analysis and proper post-training utilization of employees would result in high returns in terms of performance.

More quickly promotions, awards, and career advancement are possible if trainers are carefully chosen, and trainers' attitudes are positively shaped through training. The need to invest time and money into employee training has grown in recent years as businesses realise the value of a skilled and productive workforce

Effective training of the employees equips them to perform well and also influences the growth and sustainability of select IT companies.

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